

Hypothetical Velocity and Photon Ray Theory for Reflection/Refraction from a Moving Surface Part II

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In Part I, we argued that the hypothetical velocity approach of (1) and the photon ray theory of (2) were identical and based on the idea of a constant linked to the phase of the photon wavefunction $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = t |\mathbf{p}| (-c/n + v \cos(\theta))$ ((1)) where θ is the angle between an interface velocity vector and the \mathbf{p} vector. In the case of refraction (or reflection) from a fixed surface, there is no velocity of the interface so v is zero, while for a moving mirror or interface (of media with two different indices of refraction) there is. Thus $d\mathbf{r}(\text{vector})/dt$, in this analysis, is not the velocity vector of the photon, but rather of a moving interface. The surface of the interface (or line in 2-dimensions) yields no impulse hit, so there is conservation of the component of momentum along this line. When an interaction occurs, t in ((1)) is the same for the incident ray and the reflected and refracted, so $|\mathbf{p}| (-c/n + v \cos(\theta))$ should also be a conserved quantity, based on the photon phase.

We show how this approach gives rise to Snell's law, a relationship between the incident and reflected angle of light for a moving mirror and refraction of light for a moving interface with a different index of refraction. The point we make is that the phase of the photon remains constant in these interactions if $d\mathbf{r}(\text{vector})/dt$ is considered to be the velocity of a moving mirror or interface. In other words, there seems to be a generalization of the Lorentz invariant $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ for $d\mathbf{r}(\text{vector})/dt = \text{velocity of a surface}$ which gives rise to reflection or refraction. In other words, the reflected and refracted rays are equivalent to the incident one in that they all have the same phase: $t |\mathbf{p}| (-c/n + v \cos(\theta))$. For Snell's law, $v=0$, so the phase is $-Et$ which is constant, but is usually associated with the photon retaining the same energy whether it reflects or refracts.

Phase of a Photon and a Moving Mirror or Interface

The Lorentz invariant phase of a photon wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is:

$$-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} \quad ((2))$$

E is a constant and \mathbf{p} a constant vector for an incident ray and one may evaluate the wavefunction or phase at different t and \mathbf{r} vector values as a math function. What if there is a moving mirror or moving interface with a different index of refraction in the problem? Such a system has a velocity vector, but also a surface (or line in 2 dimensions) which does impart an impulse hit. Thus:

The momentum component along the surface of the moving object (mirror, interface) should be constant ((3))

If the surface is taken to be the x axis and motion is in the y direction, one may have various solutions, i.e. an incident ray, reflected ray and a refracted one (if there is a second medium). $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ should be continuous at such an interface, as well as its first derivative, but

this is not the same idea as the phase being constant, which we present here. (In fact, continuity may lead to minus signs which yield phase shifts of π for reflection, but we focus only on $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ with \mathbf{r} vector $/t$ being the conserved quantity.

The velocity vector for a constant v may be mapped into $d\mathbf{r}/dt$ in ((2)).

We note that: $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ is the action = $L t$ for a particle with rest mass. Thus the constant phase is like a constant action whether the particle reflects or refracts, if \mathbf{r} vector $/t$ is the velocity of a moving surface which causes reflection and refraction.

$$-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = t |\mathbf{p}| (-c/n + v \cos(\theta)) \quad \text{where } \cos(\theta) \text{ is the angle between } \mathbf{p} \text{ and } \mathbf{v}. \quad ((4))$$

For $v=0$, i.e. no moving surface in the problem, one has: $-Et = -t|\mathbf{p}|c/n$.

If the phase is constant in ((2)) in this scenario, it means E is conserved, which is the case for reflection or refraction from a fixed surface or interface. If a velocity of a mirror or interface is present, then ((2)) is the conserved quantity and not E , if $d\mathbf{r}/dt$ vector is taken to represent the velocity of the surface or interface. Why should the phase ((2)) be constant for a velocity of an interface or surface present in the system? We argue that there exists a kind of continuity of the phase after the reaction as there is a kind of time reversal present. $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{v}$ gives the component of \mathbf{p} parallel to \mathbf{v} . This is the component of \mathbf{p} which suffers an impulse hit. We argue that the reflection/refraction impulse hit is of a special nature in that it does not change the form of the wavefunction:

$$\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) = \exp(i t \text{ constant phase}) \quad ((5)), \text{ but only the values of } E \text{ and } \mathbf{p} \text{ vector.}$$

One may note that $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$, for a particle with rest mass is a Lorentz invariant as well as the action. In a rest frame, one has: $-Et = m_0 c^2 t$. Here it is as if $t |\mathbf{p}| (-c/n + v \cos(\theta))$ plays a similar role with time moving on, but the factor $|\mathbf{p}| (-c/n + v \cos(\theta))$ being the same for the incident, reflected and refracted rays as if it represents a physical property like rest mass. It in fact, represents the phase which is a physical entity in the sense that two photons with different phases interfere. In other words, simply by examining the phase (excluding any -1 factors from a coefficient), one cannot tell if the photon has reflected or refracted or is still an incident one.

Thus we argue for a kind of time reversal which allows changes in E and \mathbf{p} vector, but keeps the overall phase the same.

For Snell's law, one states that energy is conserved, while the photon ray theory argues for $E - \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ as a new Hamiltonian. We suggest that it is the quantum phase of the photon which remains constant even if E and \mathbf{p} vector change. This seems to be a generalization of the conservation of a Lorentz invariant. A Lorentz invariant is one which contains the same value if E, t, \mathbf{p} vector and \mathbf{r} vector are viewed from a frame moving at constant v . Here E and \mathbf{p} change due to an interaction (i.e. one has an incident, reflected and refracted ray), but \mathbf{v} vector is the same ((4)) and yet one still has an invariant. This conservation, however, seems to describe the

static Snell's law reflection case as well as reflection from a moving mirror and refraction from a moving interface. We now consider specific examples.

Snell's Law

Snell's law applies to refraction from a non-moving surface. Thus v vector is 0 in ((4)). In such a case: $-Et$ is conserved for the incident and refracted ray. One, however, has the conservation of the component of p along the surface i.e.

$$p_1 \sin(AA) = p_2 \sin(BB) \quad ((6))$$

$$E=pc \text{ so } E= p_1 c/n_1 = p_2 c/n_2 \quad ((7)) \rightarrow \sin(AA)/\sin(BB) = n_2/n_1 \quad ((7))$$

Reflection from a Moving Mirror

Consider a mirror lying along the x -axis and moving along the y with velocity v . Then:

$|p_1| t (1 - v \cos(AA)) = |p_2| t (1 + v \cos(BB)) \quad ((8))$ where AA and BB are the angles of p_1 , p_2 with the y -axis.

$|p_1|/|p_2| = (c/n_1 - v \cos(AA)) / (c/n_1 + v \cos(BB))$, but ((6)) still applies so one may replace

$|p_1|/|p_2|$ with $\sin(BB)/\sin(AA)$.

Refraction in a Moving Medium.

Consider an environment with n_1 in which a photon strikes an interface (with n_2) which lies along the x -axis and moves along the y -axis with velocity v . Applying conservation of phase yields:

$$-t |p_1| (c/n_1 - v \cos(AA)) = -t |p_2| (c/n_2 - v \cos(BB)) \quad ((7))$$

with ((6)) still applying.

Special Relativity

The conservation of phase for r vector/ t = velocity of interface seems to be linked to the case of special relativity. If one uses a constant v , one may imagine a frame in which the surface or interface is at rest. In such a case, one has usual reflection or refraction, so physically the phase of the photon follows the $-E + p \cdot r$ conservation in this frame. If this is a physical condition, it should then hold in other frames, namely the lab one. Why is the phase considered to be a physical condition? We argue that it gives rise to physically observable n -slit interference

patterns as well as interference between different photons and so represents a kind of physical condition.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue for a conserved photon phase $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = -|\mathbf{p}| t (c/n + \cos(\theta) v)$ where v is the velocity of a moving surface or interface in the problem which gives rise to reflection or refraction. The Lorentz invariant $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ seems to be generalized into a constant which holds even if E and \mathbf{p} change (reflected and refracted ray), but \mathbf{r}/t remains constant. It is as if there is a kind of time reversal invariance which keeps the phase the same or a physical property akin to rest mass which applies to $-|\mathbf{p}| (c/n + \cos(\theta) v)$.

We argue that the phase has a physical sense because it leads to interference between shifted photons and n-slit interference patterns. We suggest that $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ remains a constant. (although there can be a phase shift of π for reflection from $n_1 < n_2$, but this is linked with the coefficient of the wavefunction in a continuity balance of wavefunctions and their first derivative), not the phase.). Phase is conserved if one uses $\mathbf{r}/t = v$ the velocity of the moving surface in a problem of reflection or refraction.

We apply this suggestion to Snell's law, reflection from a moving mirror and refraction from a moving interface.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fermat's Principle and a Hypothetical Velocity Hypotenuse Approach (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. J.T. Mendoca, Theory of Photon Acceleration (Institute of Physics Publishing)
http://www.physics.gov.az/book_T/Mendonca.pdf